

D7.8: 1st Pro-Enrich event annual report

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Document information

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Executive summary

The Pro-Enrich event annual report is a compendium that documents different communication and dissemination activities conducted within the Pro-Enrich project.

This 1st edition of the Pro-Enrich event annual covers the period of M1 to M12 and includes consortium meetings (kick-off and 6M meeting) and partner participation in relevant events where Pro-Enrich dissemination activities have been conducted.

Different types of audiences have been targeted including the general public, the scientific community, industries and networks. Both academic and industry Pro-Enrich partners have contributed significantly to dissemination activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Pro-Enrich event annual report is a compendium that documents different communication and dissemination activities conducted within the Pro-Enrich project. This 1st edition covers the period M1 to M12. The Pro-Enrich event annual report will be updated M24 (2nd edition – D7.9) and M36 (3rd and final edition – D7.10). In the following sections, illustrative examples of activities are given for the period M1 to M12. The activities cover “consortium meetings” as well as “dissemination activities and events”. For a complete list/overview of events, see the “Dissemination & communication plan”.

2. CONSORTIUM MEETINGS

During the first year of the Pro-Enrich project (period M1 to M12) two consortium meetings have been conducted.

- Kick-off meeting, May 3.-4. 2018 at Danish Technological Institute, Taastrup, Denmark
- 6M meeting, 15.-16. November 2018, Anecoop, Valencia, Spain

2.1. Kick-off meeting

A two-day kick-off meeting was held May 3.-4. 2018 at Danish Technological Institute, Taastrup, Denmark with participation of all project partners. The kick off meeting had several purposes including

- Meet all partners face-to-face
- Describe the overall project and individual work packages
- Describe and clarify all administrative processes
- Give individual partner presentations
- Demonstration of pilot biorefinery at DTI

The meeting led to several stimulating and beneficial discussions about the overall purpose of the project and activities in the individual work packages. Especially logistical challenges and seasonal availability of biomass were addressed. Furthermore, a visit to the pilot biorefinery plant led to practical and technological discussions about how to process and biorefine the different types of biomass that are included in the project.

Picture 1. Group photo at kick-off meeting May 3.-4. 2018 at Danish Technological Institute, Taastrup, Denmark

Picture 2. Jose M^a Pinilla, NATAC, giving a presentation of work package 2 - Supply chain and quality assessment of raw materials.

Picture 3. Visit to the pilot biorefinery plant at Danish technological Institute, Taastrup, Denmark.

2.2. 6M meeting

A two-day M6 meeting was held 15.-16. November 2018, Anecoop, Valencia, Spain. The M6 meeting had several purposes including

- Status on individual work packages including deliverables
- Internal communication tools (Microsoft TEAMS)
- Pro-Enrich Advisory Board
- General update on new people in and out of the project
- Discussion of dissemination materials (Brochure, poster, roll-up, home-page)
- Site visit to ANECOOP
- Steering committee meeting

WP leaders presented status on individual work packages. This included activities conducted within the first six months of the projects. Furthermore, partners discussed and planned forthcoming activities. Project partners were informed that the internal communication platform “One Drive” has been changed to “Microsoft Teams”. A key point on the agenda was the Pro-Enrich Advisory Board. Project partners contributed with suggestions for several relevant companies, organisations and persons. A site visit to Anecoop processing facilities showed the types of citrus and other fruit side-streams and the large amounts and that are available for biorefining.

Picture 4. Site visit to Anecoop processing and packaging facilities.

Picture 5. Nicolas Juste Vidal, Anecoop, showing citrus-fruit side-streams.

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES AND EVENTS

Dissemination activities are conducted within Work Package 7 (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation), for which ABP will be mainly responsible. The 1st Dissemination & communication plan described how to disseminate to the following target groups

- All target groups (including general public)
- Research and scientific community
- Industries
- Existing networks
- Political organizations

In the following section examples of relevant activities, in relation to different target groups are given.

3.1. All target groups (including the general public)

Pro-Enrich partners have participated in events where the target group has been broad and has included the general public. Relevant events include

- Danish Bioeconomy Conference, 27th of September 2018, Sakskøbing, Denmark
- Presentation at International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy (IFIB), 27th of September 2018
- Presentation at The European Investment Bank Copenhagen conference on the circular economy, 25th of October 2018
- Presentation at Network for polymers, 6th of November 2018
- Presentation for and meeting with The Danish Agriculture & Food Council, 18th of December 2018
- Presentation of Pro-Enrich at Sustainable Packaging Workshop, 29th of January 2019
- Presentation at Bio-Based Industries Consortium - Matchmaking Event 2019, 20th of February 2019
- Presentation for the "Innovation network for Bioresources" steering group, 28th of February 2019
- Presentation at the national BBI info day at Haldor Topsøe, 2nd of April 2019

One example was the Danish Bioeconomy Conference 2018 co-organised by Agro Business Park and where a Pro-Enrich presentation was given by project coordinator Anne Christine Hastrup from the Danish Technological Institute.

The conference was attended by >150 participants from science, industry and the general public. There was a good debate with the participating companies and interest organisations following the presentation and discussion of the possibilities.

Picture 6. Pro-Enrich presentation at Danish Bioeconomy Conference 2018.

3.2. Research and scientific community

Pro-Enrich partners have participated in events where the main target group has been the research and scientific community. This includes

- Charm of Wood, 15th of May 2018, Ljubljana, Slovenia
- Presentation at 14th International Conference on Renewable Resources and Biorefineries (RRB-14), 30th of May 2018
- RTO Innovations Summit, 6th of November 2018, Bruxelles, Belgium
- Presentation at International Society of Wood Science and Technology conference, 7th of November, 2018
- Exhibitor at North Wales Means Business Conference & Showcase, 29th of November, 2018
- Presentation at COST Action FP1407 Final Conference: "Living with modified wood", 12th of December, 2018

The RTO Innovation Summit was the first event of its kind organized jointly by ten major European Research and Technology Organizations (RTOs) including the Danish Technological Institute. The Summit took place against the background of the ongoing preparations for the future EU research framework program »Horizon Europe« and focused on creating impact through (applied) research. The event was attended by a wide range of policy makes and companies.

Pro-Enrich was presented by Anne Christine Hastrup, Danish Technological Institute in the session on Biological Transformation, which focused on the effect that biotech has on economies and societies around the globe. The systematic application of principles, resources and processes of nature in technology will enable entire new technological solutions and high-tech markets, leading to far-reaching social and economic change processes. Biological Transformation is empowered by progress in life sciences, advances in digitalization, as well as

in material and production sciences. Essential challenges of today’s societies can finally be addressed – with sustainable growth strategies and lasting efficiency that affects all areas of value creation.

Picture 7. Anne Christine Hastrup, Danish Technological Institute presenting Pro-Enrich at the RTO Summit, 2018

THE RTO INNOVATION SUMMIT

Pro-Enrich

- Extraction of functional ingredients through cascading biorefining in generic infrastructure

Anne Christine S. Hastrup, Ph.D.
Danish Technological Institute

Bio-based Industries Consortium

BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES
Public-Private Partnership

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Picture 8. Pro-Enrich presentation at RTO Innovations Summit, 2018 by Danish Technological Institute.

The Charm of Wood is an exhibition that promotes wood and wood products. 2018 was the 10th year that the Association for the Protection of Wood of Slovenia, the Ministry of Economic Development and Technology, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food, the SPIRIT Slovenia – Public Agency of the Republic of Slovenia, the Department of wood science and technology at the Biotechnical faculty, and the Wood Council, in cooperation with Cankarjev dom organized the event. The organizers of the exhibition also prepared a scientific conference »The role of science in wood innovations« which took place on Tuesday 15th May. The director

of the InnoRenew CoE, Dr Andreja Kutnar moderated the conference. Among eight speakers three were researchers of the InnoRenew CoE – Dr Jure Pohleven, Dr Michael Burnard, and Dr Matthew Schwarzkopf. The event was attended by academics in the fields of bio-materials, Mediterranean agriculture, and students from primary and secondary schools. In addition to the exhibition, the organizers also prepared an accompanying program full of expert consultations and roundtable discussions on wood and lectures and workshops for children. Dr. Matthew Schwarzkopf presented the Pro-Enrich project, its partners, objectives, outputs, and links to other wood-related innovations that InnoRenew has been researching. This presentation and event gained exposure for the Pro-Enrich project to a diverse field of academics that are interested in similar work as well as getting youth interested in the field of biorefining and agricultural best practices.

Picture 9. Matthew Schwarzkopf, InnoRenew, presenting Pro-Enrich at Charm of Wood event, 2018

3.3. Industries

Pro-Enrich partners have participated in several events where the main audience is industry. The events include

- IFIB - International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy, 27th September 2018, Torino, Italy

- FIMART - Feria para la Innovación Smart Rural (Fair for Smart Rural Innovation), 16th – 18th October 2018, Córdoba, Spain
- ALIBETOPIAS, 18th October, 2018, Madrid, Spain
- ICIBB 2019, International Conference on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioprocessing, 21st-22nd March 2019, London, UK.

In these events, the partners were able to display Pro-Enrich posters, and in FIMART, even set up a booth with project information. This kind of events have allowed partners not only to carry out dissemination and communication on Pro-Enrich, but also to catch up with the latest news on rural and agricultural innovations, bioeconomy and bioprocessing, as well as to interact with other projects, companies and relevant stakeholders.

Especially in FIMART, where attendants could approach the booth, Pro-Enrich attracted many people interested by the possibility of obtaining functional proteins and ingredients from actual waste.

In addition, these events were a good place for networking with other BBI and H2020 projects, enhancing collaboration to transition towards bioeconomy.

Picture 10. Irene Paredes, Innovarum, presenting a Pro-Enrich poster at IFIB 2018.

Picture 11. Nicolas Juste Vidal, Anecoop, presenting Pro-Enrich at the ALIBETOPIAS event.

3.4. Existing networks

Pro-Enrich partners has been in contact with several relevant networks and organisations. The networks and organisations that has been contacted include

- The Innovation Network for Bioresources
- COPA-COGECA
- Danish Environment Technology Associations (DETA)

The Pro-Enrich project was presented for the steering group of the Innovation Network for Bioresources (INBIOM) on the 28th of February 2019 at Daka, Dakavej 6, 8722 Hedensted, Denmark. The INBIOM steering group includes representatives from all major Danish universities, RTOs, regional and national authorities, trade organisations, small and large enterprises (Table 1). After presentation of the Pro-Enrich project, discussions included how more SME can benefit from knowledge and competences at universities and RTOs. The discussion also included how to support a RIA project (low TRL) to the next IA level (mid TRL).

Table 1: Members of the INBIOM steering group:

- Aarhus University
- Aalborg University
- Copenhagen University
- Danish Technological University
- FORCE
- Danish Technological Institute
- Agro Business Park
- NIRAS
- Association of the biogas industry
- Hedeselskabet

- The Confederation of Danish Industry
- Central Denmark Region
- Agro Intelligence
- The Danish Environmental Protection Agency

The Pro-Enrich project was presented at Bio-Based Industries Consortium - Matchmaking Event on the 20th of February 2019 in Brussels, Belgium. Agro Business Park organised the workshop “Opportunities for the bio-based industries FEEDSTOCK DRIVEN; Agri-Food” which included a Pro-Enrich presentation by DTI and a presentation by COPA-COGECA. The presentation was followed by an interactive discussion with workshop participants. The subjects that were discussed included logistical challenges, quality of biomass, technology- and business case challenges as well as possible improvements/solutions. A main outcome of the workshop was also the identified need to improve “bioeconomy” communication to and interaction with EU citizens.

Picture 12. INBIOM steering group meeting. DAKA was host for the meeting.

Picture 13. Kell Andersen, Agro Business Park organised an Agri-Food workshop at BIC match-making event 2019.

Picture 14. Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup, Danish Technological Institute and project coordinator, presented Pro-Enrich at the BIC match-making event 2019

3.5. Political organizations

Bangor University have been active in attracting political organisations and has had political representatives participating in two project related events so far. The first meeting was a meeting with Peter Halligan and Robert Hoyle (Dr. Robert Hoyle, Chief Scientific Officer, Welsh Government Office for Science, Department for Economy and Transport, Welsh Government) on 11th of October 2018. On 17th of January 2019 the project was presented to the staff from the Welsh Government- International Relations Office. This included the Geographical Lead Officers Steve Davies (India and the Middle East), Jon Fitzgerald (North America & Europe) and Stuart Lyden (China & Japan).

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Figure 1. Reference to project’s funding bodies

ANNEXES
